

Fragments II
by Brian Paul Kaess

1. "Albert Camus or Voltaire would never persecute non-Christians. So, if you persecute non-Christians, then you are not anything about Albert Camus."
2. "O Wise one who came to subdue the princes and prelates of this world. He appeared in great brightness, He threw the diadem from their heads, and fettered the tyrants of the earth, He threw down the fire-worshippers and their temples, He closed the doors of Hades so that the righteous might not be shut inside, He brought the Light and set it in its place, He blocked the troubled waters, and uprooted the Darkness. He raised up those that fell, and healed those that were wounded. He spread out the great sea, and set barks upon it with men of truth, who spread across the earth. So, on those ships of Light shall your souls go aboard. He gave Light to the eyes of the Righteous, and gathered those that were scattered, the poor ones of Darkness. And Brightness was set upon them, a diadem was well-placed, so that they might add to the number of angels. So then arose the ranks of the Exalted from the sons of Light.

And so he came in peace, the son of Light, filled with richness and brightness. The demons were planning evil in their hearts, saying one thing, yet planning another. They wished to shut him up in a cage, for they cared not for the truth, and loved not their fellow man. But the great Light spoke and said it was not possible for the son of Light to enter through the gates of darkness, and so he must be warned. For let not the Lion take my daughter and seize her in his lair with the dragon, without my cry calling out to the Mighty One. I took my daughter away from them and set her there upon high, while the great dragon and serpent were enmeshed. And there was a man weeping down in the abyss, and his cry was lifted up. Here mercy was shown. From the heights of truth do the Holy find rest. Let Darkness be blotted from its place, and he that is cast in stocks be released. Let the Holy one speak, for indeed he has spoken. And the bride shall go to her bride-chamber. For we dig rivers with the spade of truth, so that righteousness might flow. For we wish to plant a garden beyond the confines of this world. For the Mighty one questions me, and the Righteous shall examine me. For in the world below, be aware of that place where evil waxes greatly. Tune your virtue like the strings of a lyre. Let not my soul stray and become faint. Lift up your eyes to the land of Light: you shall see the friend of the Righteous standing beyond the world.

So Love me with your heart, rather than please me with your lips. I would be like a jar of wine set upon its stand. For outside is a covered pitch, while inside is a fragrant wine. For I am the physician that heals not the wounds, but rather the soul. Do not curse another, lest you sling silent arrows into the heart. Be wary of what you do, for even the lawless judge and know how to sit upon a throne. For did not Salome build a rock upon truth and mercy. For the floor of His house is truth and faith is His front door. Let the heart seek after gladness. So then, we have arrived to the Land of Light." (adapted from the Manichaeans)